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Influence of gas mixture on fatigue life of ion (plasma) nitrided low alloy steel: Experimental and numerical studies

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Abstract

Low alloy steel grade 31CrMoV9 steels were ion nitrided at different gas mixtures of nitrogen and hydrogen. The fatigue behavior of untreated and all nitrided samples was studied with rotating bending fatigue tester. The fracture surfaces of the samples were also observed with utilizing environmental scanning electron microscope (ESEM) after fatigue tests. Results exhibited that the fatigue strength improved with rising amount of hydrogen in gas mixtures and typical subsurface fish eye crack formation was observed in all ion nitrided samples. Afterwards, the fatigue performance of untreated and nitrided samples was also examined by finite element analysis (FEA). Experimental and theoretical outcomes are compared. It was found that experimental fatigue life outcomes were close to theoretical test outcomes. Hence, the model utilized in the article is appropriate to define the fatigue performance of ion nitrided steels without experimental analyzes.

Keywords: 31CrMoV9 substrate ; Fatigue behaviour; Gas mixture; Ion nitriding; Finite element analysis

1. Introduction

Fatigue, fracture, wear and corrosion have been identified as some of big troubles in failure of engineering components. Fatigue generally associated with surface of materials is one of the most significant failure mechanisms [1-5]. It is well-known that the fatigue life of materials may be risen by improving surface hardness, providing compressive residual stress, obtaining hard layers on surface of steels. Thus, surface treatment techniques are applied to engineering materials to improve fatigue performance of them.

Ion nitriding is an effective surface hardening method that may be utilized to develop fatigue life, wear performance, and corrosion resistance for engineering components. The popularity of the method is gradually increasing due to its advantages like low treatment temperature, no pollution, short nitriding time, clean environment, and low energy consumption. Additionally, the method is suitable for materials (such as, low alloy steels, titanium alloys, etc.) which are difficult to nitride with gas nitriding and salt bath nitriding [6-8].

The influence of ion nitriding parameters (time, temperature, gas mixture ratio etc.) on fatigue behaviour of low alloy steels previously reported in the scientific studies. H. Riazi et al. indicated that the generation of the hard surface layer including compressive residual stresses is the influential factor against fatigue failure and they obtained that fatigue life of material rose with increasing nitriding time. The increment was related to formation of compressive residual stresses in layer. Because more nitrogen atoms will diffuse to material surface during the longer nitriding time at the same temperature and gas mixture ratio. As a result, higher residual stresses occur [9]. H. Kovacı et al. discovered that fatigue life of the steel material improved with nitriding process because of rising surface hardness and compressive residual stresses. Also, they said that as treatment temperature rises from 400°C to 500°C, fatigue life of steel increased [10]. A. Alsaran et al. observed an efficacy of nitriding parameters on fatigue life of ion nitrided AISI 5140. Results exhibited that structure of nitrided layer was impressed with variation nitriding parameters (temperature, time and gas mixture ratio). Also, they demonstrated that fatigue life of ion nitrided steel material improved with increasing temperature, hydrogen potential and time [11].

The present calculation technology ensures probabilities that were formerly unattainable with analytical techniques. The use of numerical methods, especially the finite element analysis (FEA), can provide to more exactly predict the fatigue properties of materials. In this content, having a previous information about fatigue life of test samples via the finite element method without experimental research is very significant with regards to cost and time. On the other hand, it is possible to define the fatigue behavior of ion nitrided samples by finite element analysis and some papers were published on fatigue features of treated samples. F. Yıldız et al. [12] compared experimental fatigue performance results of the untreated and nitrided material to finite element analysis results. They indicated that fatigue behavior outcomes of FEA were close to experimental outcomes and FEA is available to detect the fatigue properties of ion nitrided materials. J. Sawick et al. indicated that it is possible to predict the fatigue life of nitrided steels with utilize of finite element method [13]. In this case, features of plasma nitrided

samples should be transferred to software to define an effect of ion nitriding on fatigue features. So, the models of the nitrided samples would be thought in various ways. For example, some features (elastic modulus, fatigue life, elasticity modulus, and poisson ratio) of the nitrided layer and substrate desired to investigate analysis in any FEA software may be severally described. Besides, fatigue life values of substrate and nitride layer should be suitable for performing the FEA based fatigue analysis. It is reasonable to obtain information about fatigue behaviour of base material from fatigue tests, but it is not probable to obtain a fatigue life value from nitrided layer as material feature. As a result, it can be more suitable to think nitrided layer and substrate as the single part for fatigue test.

Different from other studies, there are not enough studies dealing with experimental investigation and numerical prediction of the fatigue performance of ion nitrided 31CrMoV9 steel at various gas mixtures. Hence, the basic purpose of the work is to research fatigue features of ion nitrided 31CrMoV9 steel under various nitrogen amounts. Besides fatigue performances of untreated and nitrided samples were examined by the FEA.

2. Experimental Details

The experimentations were performed on fatigue samples produced from 31CrMoV9 steel, which chemical compositions are illustrated in Table 1. The standard sample measurements given in Figure 1 was utilized. The surfaces of the samples manufactured on the CNC machine were also grinded with SiC grinding papers. Fatigue samples were placed as cathode inside into a vacuum chamber and chamber was to be vacuumed to 36×10^{-6} bar. The surface of samples were surfaces cleaned with hydrogen sputtering to against contamination for 35 minutes under a voltage of 295 V and a pressure of 0.05 bar. Afterwards, the ion nitriding was carried out in a hydrogen and nitrogen atmosphere of 0.5, 0.3, and 0.1 N_2/N_2+H_2 , at a temperature of 500°C for 4 h under a pressure of 0.05 bar. For the phase identification, XRD analyses were carried out with utilizing X-ray diffractometer. The Co-K α radiation with a wave length of 1.790300Å was utilized for both XRD analyses. The diffraction was conducted with a scanning from 15° to 90°. Residual stresses were measured by XRD utilizing the $\sin^2\psi$ technique. Environmental scanning electron microscope (ESEM) examinations were performed to carry out the cross-section image of the nitrided layer and the fracture surfaces. The microhardness investigations of untreated and nitrided samples were measured by microhardness tester at a constant load of 15gr. and 20s hold time. Elastic modulus were defined by nano indentation method. Nanoindentation tests were carried out at 10 mN and penetration depth of 500 nm. The hardness values were measured in six various locations on the steel sample. Fatigue tests were

investigated by employing rotating bending fatigue tester at 2400 rev./min. and performed until the complete failure of samples and the stress ratio was -1 . Twenty-six samples were utilized for defining the S-N curves of untreated and ion nitrided steel fatigue samples. Staircase technique was also used to define fatigue life. If the samples were not suffering fatigue damage after 10^6 cycles, the tests were finished. Finite element analysis (FEA) was performed using ANSYS-Workbench commercial package program. Figure 2a exhibited the three-dimensional fatigue sample that were utilized in the analysis. The meshed model of the fatigue sample with high quality meshing are displayed in Figure 2b. These models included 2376 elements and 11492 nodes for the fatigue sample. Fully reversed loading type was performed for finite element analysis. The "Goodman" approach was also used as mean stress theory. Figure 3 displays the constraints and loading condition of the ion nitrided fatigue samples.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Microstructural and morphological evaluations

The X-ray diffraction patterns of the untreated and nitrided samples at different gas mixture are displayed in Figure 4. According to XRD results, untreated steel structure consists of a completely entirely of α -Fe (ferrite iron) phase and only ferrite iron peaks were detected. The surface phase is a new ferrite (α -Fe phase), but the (1 1 0) and (2 0 0) diffraction peaks all shift toward to higher diffraction angle, showing that the compressive stress was fabricated by ion nitriding. M.F. Yan et al. [14] pointed out that compressive stress is one of the most substantial determinants to increase fatigue life of the metallic materials. Furthermore, it was investigated that nitride phases indicates diffraction peaks with lower intensity owing to smaller thickness of compound layer at lower the quantity of nitrogen in gas mixture. Since, low nitrogen level was convenient for denitriding. Figure 5 shows the correlation between incident angles and residual stress values. Stress situation changed with ion nitriding compressive residual stresses appeared in the nitrided layers. The five various incident angle (ω) values were used to detect residual-stress variation with depth. X-Ray beams go deeper in increment of ω values and the compressive residual stress values are obtained in deeper zone with higher ω values. Thus, the residual stresses diminished from near the surface to the deeper regions [15]. The measured highest of stress at the deepest zone were found from in gas atmosphere composed of 90% of H_2 and 10% of N_2 compared to other nitriding conditions at maximum incident angles ($\omega= 7$ and 9°) as seen Figure 5. The compressive residual stresses ensure the beneficial efficacy for retardation of crack formation. As a results, there is positive affect of compressive residual stress formation on fatigue behavior of metallic materials. Figure 6 displays the microstructures

of the cross-sections of ion-nitrided samples. It was seen that thickness of the nitrided layers changed depending on gas mixture ratios. The thickness of this layer was increased with raising amount of hydrogen in the gas atmosphere. Besides, the highest thickness value was taken from the in gas mixture composed of 90% of H₂ and 10% of N₂. It may be explained that as the amount of hydrogen increased with raising hydrogen potential, the high voltage required to obtain treatment temperature of 500 °C. It was also seen an increase in the amount of ionized gas owing to applied large voltage. Hereby, the increment in the nitrided layer can indicated with raising of hydrogen potential. [16]. Figure 7 illustrates the hardness profiles of microhardness indentations of the ion nitrided samples. The surface hardness values of ion nitrided samples in all cases were higher than that of untreated steel sample. Also, highest hardness values were taken from sample ion nitrided with 0.5 N₂/N₂+H₂ gas mixture. An increase in indent dimension is an evidence of decreasing hardness and the hardness diminish from the surface to internal structure (core) due to reduction of the intensity of metal nitrides.

3.2. Fatigue behavior

S-N curves of the untreated and ion-nitrided samples was shown in Figure 8. An increment in the fatigue life of 31CrMoV9 steel was observed after ion nitriding. The fatigue behavior's improvement can be ascribed to retardation in the rate of fatigue crack growth owing to the high hardness and compression residual stresses. The reason is that compression residual stresses are occurred with precipitation of metal nitrides and result of nitrogen redistribution in γ -Fe phase. Also, the formation of precipitated nitrides stops the dislocation movement. So, the movement of slip bands on the surface of material form just at high-stress levels. If the movement of slip bands prevents, crack initiation delays [17,18]. When the curves are examined, fatigue strength of nitrided samples raised with the increase of the amount of hydrogen in gas mixture. This increment can be related to the nitrided layer which increases with the increase of hydrogen potential, according to Table2. Because the nitrided layer consists of compression residual stress and it is seen that thickness nitrided layer is directly proportional to the increasing residual stress depth. Besides, the highest fatigue strength was obtained from gas mixture ratio of 0.1 N₂/N₂+H₂. Figure 9 exhibits SEM imagines of fatigue fracture surface of ion nitrided samples. The characteristic subsurface fish eye crack creation were obtained from all treated samples. In normally, crack for homogeneous materials starts on the surface. But, crack initiation on the surface is prevented by the increase in the hardness of the nitrided samples. As a result, cracks starts easier under the hard nitrided layer as fish-eye. Some researchers indicated that the crack initiation originates from nonmetallic inclusion in fish-eye. The inclusions do not adapt

mechanically, physically and chemically with its environment. So, cracks occurs when they subjected to tensile stress. On the other hand, transgranular cleavage and transgranular ductile fractures are seen inside and outside of fish eyes, respectively. It is investigated that fish-eye size increased with the increment of the amount of hydrogen in gas mixture. It was also known that the size of the fish eye is directly proportional to the fatigue life. This implies that the increase of residual stress depth leads to the increase of fish-eye size because, the fatigue crack growth life is much longer under higher residual stress depth [19,20].

3.3. Finite element analysis

The comparison between the finite element (FE) analysis and experimental outcomes is given in the Figure 10 for untreated samples. Firstly, mechanical features (The elasticity modulus $E = 198\text{GPa}$, poisson ratio $\nu = 0.3$, and yield strength $\sigma_{\text{yield}} = 550\text{MPa}$) and the fatigue life values of the 31CrMoV9 steel were entered into the finite element software. According to results, it can be said that there is favorable accordance between the experimental and theoretical life outcomes. It is necessary to transfer the properties of the ion nitrided fatigue sample to the program to indicate an effect of the ion nitriding technique on the fatigue properties of the parts via finite element analysis. On the other hands, thinking independently of layer and base material does not seem appropriate in terms of being able to perform fatigue analysis in the finite element analysis. So, the ion-nitrided material should be considered as a whole. Because of this, the fatigue properties and elasticity modulus of the ion-nitrided fatigue samples must determine in order to perform the finite element method. Guagliano and Vergani suggested a model find out elasticity modulus of the treated steel samples via utilizing two parallel springs. Hence, an approach was utilized to calculate the elastic modulus of the ion nitrided fatigue samples in this present study [21]. Also, figure 11 showed details of the approach schematically and equation3 was utilized.

$$K_{\text{total}} = K_{\text{layer}} + K_{\text{core}} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{E_{\text{total}} \cdot A_{\text{total}}}{L} = \frac{E_{\text{layer}} \cdot A_{\text{layer}}}{L} + \frac{E_{\text{core}} \cdot A_{\text{core}}}{L} \quad (2)$$

$$E_{\text{total}} = \frac{E_{\text{layer}} \cdot A_{\text{layer}} + E_{\text{core}} \cdot A_{\text{core}}}{A_{\text{total}}} \quad (3)$$

E_{total} , A_{total} , E_{layer} , A_{layer} , E_{core} , and A_{core} are the elasticity modulus of treated steel, cross-sectional area of treated steel, the elasticity modulus of a nitrided layer, the cross-sectional area of the nitrided layer, the elasticity modulus of the substrate and cross-sectional area of the substrate in equations, respectively. The elastic modulus values were calculated from equation 3 are listed in Table 3. Also, elasticity modulus and fatigue features values of ion nitrided samples at various gas mixture transferred to the software. Figure 12 shows experimental and theoretical S-N curves of ion nitrided fatigue samples in a gas mixture of 0.5, 0.3, and 0.1 N_2/N_2+H_2 . The experimental values are close to theoretical life values. Therefore, it was observed that Guagliano and Vergani approach and the model provided positive results for nitrided samples and mechanical elements. According to these results, having a preliminary data about the fatigue strength and life of nitrided parts with the finite element method without performed test is very significant with regards to time and cost loss to be prevented.

4. Conclusions

In this article, influence of different gas mixture ratios on fatigue performance of ion nitrided steel were carried out. After ion nitriding, the fatigue strength for 31CrMoV9 steel increased approximately 50-67 % depending on thickness of the diffusion layer and compressive residual stress depth. The deeper diffusion zones and compressive residual stress distributions lead to higher fatigue strength. However, it was not seen that compound layer has influential factor for fatigue performance of nitrided sample. After fatigue tests, the fish eyes were seen on the fracture surfaces and the inclusions were almost formed at the center of fish-eyes. It was also observed that fish-eye size increased with the increment of the amount of hydrogen in gas mixture. On the other hand, experimental and theoretical analyzes were compared for untreated and ion-nitrided in gas mixture ratio of 0.5, 0.3, and 0.1 N_2/N_2+H_2 fatigue samples. It was also found that theoretical outcomes were close to experimental results. Thus, the model applied in the article is useful to detect fatigue behaviour of ion nitrided fatigue samples.

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Table 1. Chemicala composition of 31CrMoV9 steel (wt %)

% C	% Si	% Mn	% Al	% P	% Cr	% Mo	% Ni	% Cu
0.35	0.37	0.53	0.11	0.015	1.72	0.19	0.019	0.06

Table 2. The compound and diffusion layer thicknesses, surface hardness and fatigue strength under different hydrogen potential

Nitriding parameters			Nitrided layer [μm]	Surface hardness, [$\text{H}_{0.01}$]	Fatigue Strength [MPa]
Temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	Time [h]	Gas mixture ($\text{N}_2/\text{N}_2+\text{H}_2$)			
500	4	0.5	186-199	874-878	420
500	4	0.3	213-216	820-835	450
500	4	0.1	296-303	774-777	500
Untreated 31CrMoV9 steel			-	298-308	300

Table 3. The values of elastic modulus of ion nitrided samples with different gas mixtures

Gas mixture ($\text{N}_2/\text{N}_2+\text{H}_2$)	E_{layer} (GPa)	A_{layer} (mm^2)	E_{core} (GPa)	A_{layer} (mm^2)	E_{total} (GPa)
0.5	250	4.731	198	45.509	202.8
0.3	248	5.256	198	44.984	203.1
0.1	234	7.25	198	42.991	203.3

Figure 1. Fatigue test sample, dimensions in mm

Figure 2. a-) 3D fatigue model, b-) The mesh of fatigue sample

Figure 3. Boundary Condition of fatigue sample

Figure 4. XRD results of untreated and ion nitrided samples

Figure 5. Compressive residual stresses measured from ion nitrided samples at varied incident angles.

Figure 6. Cross-section SEM micrograph of 31CrMoV9 steel after ion nitriding at gas mixture of a-) 0.5, b-) 0.3, and c-) 0.1 (N_2/N_2+H_2)

Figure 7. The hardness profiles of ion nitrided 31CrMoV9 steel under different hydrogen potential

Figure 8. Fatigue life curves for ion nitrided 31CrMoV9 steel under different different hydrogen potential

Figure 9. SEM micrographs of fracture surface of the sample ion nitrided at gas mixture of a-) 0.5, b-) 0.3, and c-) 0.1 N_2/N_2+H_2

Figure 10. Experimental and theoretical S-N curves of untreated sample

Figure 11. a-) Schematic exhibition of nitrided part, b-) spring model of nitrided sample

Figure 12. Experimental and theoretical S-N curves of ion nitrided samples at different hydrogen potential

Highlights

- In order to increase fatigue performance of 31CrMoV9 steel, plasma nitriding was performed.
- The influences of gas mixture on fatigue performances of plasma nitrided sample were investigated.
- The fatigue performance of untreated and plasma-nitrided 31CrMoV9 steel was examined by the finite element method.
- Theoretical outcomes are compared with that taken from experiments.